

Tool 16

Communication and engagement plan

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 2 – develop), which helps you to develop a communication and engagement plan. This template is developed by the authors of the handbook ‘[A practical guide to communication and engagement in citizen science](#)’, published by Scivil.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact info@scivil.be.

1. Target groups

Who is/are your primary target audience(s)?

Who is/are your secondary target audience(s)?

Who are the intermediaries (consider organisations which are in contact with your primary target audience)?

Describe your target audiences as accurately as possible by means of the following characteristics:

	Target audience I	Target audience II	Target audience III
Demographics (age, gender, profession, socio-economic profile, etc.)			
Prior knowledge or skills related to science and the thematic topic or your research (project)			
Current behaviour related to the thematic topic			
Technological skills (smartphone, mobile apps, laptop usage, social media skills, etc.)			
Potential barriers and motivations to participate			

Does your project need a diverse and inclusive target audience?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

2. Define the strategy of your communication and engagement plan

What approach will you take in your communication plan?

- *Generic approach*
- *Specific approach*
- *Generic and specific approach*

What is your total communication budget?

Which communication and engagement tactics and tools will you apply? Choose from the list below:

- Social media:
 - Page about my project on Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, ...
 - Paid advertisements
 - Open or closed Facebook groups for community members
 - WhatsApp support groups
 -
- Gamification
- Storytelling
 - Digital storytelling
 - Creative slogans
 -
- Ambassadors
- Social events
 - Public exhibitions
 - Get to know the community
 -
- Events
 - Workshops
 - Conference
 - Webinar
 -
- Measurement campaigns
 - Seasonal campaigns
 - Theme based campaigns
 - Topically-based campaigns
 -
- Printed material
 - Brochure
 - Leaflet
 - Postcards
 - Bookmarks

- Posters
-
- Website
- Press releases
- Newsletters
- Videos
- Scientific publications
- Personal communication
 - One to one mailing
 - One to one phone calls
- Mass media
 - TV commercial
 - Radio spot
 - Public screens
 - Newspaper advertisement
 -
- Projects and activities in Science Communication (cf. the offer by VUB's Research Outreach & Communication Office, Phase 3, [Tool 18](#))

*If you aim for inclusive citizen science, how will you engage underrepresented groups?
(cfr. Inclusiveness checklist)*

What channels are most suitable for your target audiences? Fill in the table below with the chosen target groups on top and the communication & engagement channels to the left (with a potential overlap between target audiences and channels):

	<i>Target audience I:</i>	<i>Target audience II:</i>	<i>Target audience III:</i>
<i>Channel 1:</i>			
<i>Channel 2:</i>			
<i>Channel 3:</i>			
<i>Channel 4:</i>			
<i>Channel 5:</i>			
....			

3. Microplanning

Timing			
Goal			
Target audience			
Main message (content for the target group)			
Tactic or channel			
Responsible person			
Cost estimation			

4. Evaluation

Will you evaluate your communication and engagement plan?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Which quantitative and qualitative indicators do you want to check in your evaluation? Potential indicators might be:

Quantitative

- Number of social media subscribers
- Number of website visits
- Number of events
- Number of newsletter subscribers
- Number of press releases
- The number of scientific publications
- Share of participants from underrepresented groups
-

Qualitative

- Satisfaction with the results of the process
- Effectiveness of the communication: consistency of messages
- Effectiveness of the communication: continuity of messages
- Democracy of the process (fair, open)
- Changes in knowledge, attitudes or behaviours
-